

Evaluation Of Salivary Matrix Metalloproteinase-8 Levels in Chronic Periodontitis Patients Treated with Ozonated Olive Oil Gel as An Adjunct to Non-Surgical Periodontal Therapy

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ABSTRACT

Scaling and root planing (SRP) is the gold standard treatment for periodontitis, effectively reducing bacterial load and promoting periodontal healing. To improve treatment outcomes, adjunctive therapies such as antimicrobial agents, probiotics, laser therapy, and ozone applications have been investigated. **Materials and Methods:** A total of 40 patients aged 25-55 years diagnosed with stage II periodontitis were divided randomly into 2 groups. Plaque Index (PI), Gingival Index (GI), Pocket Depth (PD), and Clinical Attachment Level (CAL) were recorded. Unstimulated saliva samples were collected to estimate MMP-8 levels. Group I (n=20) received SRP plus ozonated olive oil, while Group II (n=20) received SRP plus placebo (mineral) oil. All the patients were recalled after 3 months for re-evaluation. **Results:** At baseline, mean PI and GI were similar between groups. After 3 months, both groups showed significant reductions in PI and GI with no significant intergroup difference. PD reduced significantly in Group I from 5.41 mm to 3.25 mm and in Group II from 5.33 mm to 3.79 mm ($p = 0.001$). CAL improved significantly from 5.68 mm to 3.71 mm in Group I and from 5.79 mm to 4.28 mm in Group II ($p < 0.001$). sMMP-8 levels decreased markedly in both groups, with Group I showing a greater reduction (6.34 to 1.30 ng/ml) than Group II (6.41 to 2.61 ng/ml). **Conclusions:** The study demonstrated that both treatment groups experienced significant improvements in periodontal health over a 3-month period. Application of OOIL exhibited greater reductions in PD, CAL, and sMMP-8 levels compared to placebo.

Keywords: Matrix Metalloproteinases, Olive Oil, Periodontitis, Root Planing, Saliva.

INTRODUCTION

Periodontal therapies, both surgical and nonsurgical, are used to treat periodontitis by removing the biofilm and calculus deposits from the crown and root surfaces as well as by restoring the normal structure and function of periodontium.¹ Scaling and root planing (SRP) is the gold standard treatment for periodontitis, effectively reducing bacterial load and promoting periodontal healing.² However, achieving complete removal of subgingival plaque and calculus during SRP is challenging, as residual microbial contamination may lead to disease recurrence. To improve treatment outcomes, adjunctive therapies such as antimicrobial agents, probiotics, laser therapy, and ozone applications have been investigated.^{3,4}

Over time, several antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory agents have been applied sub-gingivally to treat periodontal diseases, showing notable outcomes. According to Figuero et al, antibiotics administered sub-gingivally release the active ingredients for a permitted amount of time at a predefined therapeutic level for enhanced effect on lowering the counts of periodontopathogens, decrease probing depths, and lessen bleeding on probing.⁵

Ozone (O₃), a powerful oxidizing agent with antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, and immunomodulatory properties, has gained attention in periodontal therapy. Ozone is a colorless gas form of oxygen that is existent in atmosphere. When three atoms of oxygen are subjected to ultraviolet (UV)

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rays, ozone gas is formed.⁶ The main use of ozone therapy in dentistry depends on its antimicrobial properties which disrupts bacterial cell envelope by oxidation of lipoproteins and phospholipids. It also has analgesic, immunostimulant, and wound healing properties.⁶ Olive oil, obtained from the fruit of the olive tree (*Olea europaea*) primarily found in Mediterranean regions, is well-known for its substantial health benefits. Extra Virgin Olive Oil mainly comprises stearic acid, linoleic acid, palmitoleic acid, and palmitic acid. It also contains trace amounts of flavonoids, β -carotene, tocopherol, and phenols.⁷ Moreover, olive oil is rich in hydroxytyrosol, an antioxidant with anti-inflammatory and anti-teratogenic properties, which also helps reduce oxidative damage.⁸

Ozonation of olive oil modifies its chemical makeup and produces ozonides, aldehydes, and peroxides that boost biological activity. Findings suggest that ozonated olive oil exhibits higher peroxide numbers along with stronger antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties.⁹

MMP-8 is considered to be one of the promising biomarkers for periodontitis in oral fluids. During inflammation, neutrophils release matrix metalloproteinase-8 (MMP-8) through selective degranulation in response to periopathogens, their virulence factors, and host-derived proinflammatory mediators. Elevated MMP-8 levels in oral fluids such as saliva, gingival crevicular fluid (GCF), and peri-implant sulcular fluid (PISF) have been associated with key clinical periodontal parameters, including probing pocket depth, bleeding on probing, and clinical attachment loss.¹⁰ Saliva serves as an ideal diagnostic fluid for assessing oral health, particularly periodontitis, due to its easy availability and non-invasive collection process.¹¹ Whole saliva is a diagnostic medium for periodontal disease because it contains systemic and local derived biomarkers, periodontal pathogens and also cariogenic microorganisms.¹²

Previous studies by Butera et al., Nambiar et al., and Sharma et al. compared ozonized gel and ozonated olive oil with chlorhexidine gel, reporting significant reductions in clinical parameters in the ozone group.¹³⁻¹⁵

This is the first study to evaluate ozonated olive oil as a subgingival application and to assess MMP-8 levels in Stage II periodontitis patients. The aim of this study is to evaluate salivary MMP-8 levels in chronic periodontitis patients following the application of ozonated olive oil as an adjunct to non-surgical periodontal therapy (NSPT).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Patients aged 25-55 years diagnosed with Stage II periodontitis and visiting the Out-Patient Department of Periodontics, Sibar Institute of Dental Sciences, Andhra Pradesh, were included in the study. Eligible patients were informed about the study objectives and methods, and written informed consent was obtained from each participant. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee under protocol number Pr.100/IEC/SIBAR/2022. The study was registered with the Clinical Trial Registry of India (CTRI) under registration number CTRI/2022/06/042993. The trial adhered to the principles of the Helsinki Declaration (2013) and followed CONSORT guidelines throughout. The study flowchart is presented in Figure 1.

Sample size calculation: Sample size calculation was performed using G*Power software (G power 3.1.9.2, Dusseldorf, Germany). The α -error was set at 0.05, and the effect size was calculated as 0.91. With a statistical power of 0.8, the total sample size determined was 40, comprising 20 patients in each group. **Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:** Participants who were healthy individuals aged 35–55 years with generalized probing pocket depth and clinical attachment level ≥ 5 mm, radiographic evidence of horizontal bone loss, and who provided informed consent for the study were included into the study. Subjects with radiographic evidence of vertical bone loss, a history of drug allergy, any form of tobacco use, pregnancy or lactation, or a history of periodontal therapy within the past year were excluded from the study.

Study Design: A total of 40 quadrants in 40 patients were recruited and divided randomly into 2 groups with the help of a computer-generated random sequencing of numbers with ratio of 1:1. Group-I (n=20) were treated with SRP+ ozonated olive oil,

whereas Group II (n=20) were treated with SRP+ placebo oil (Mineral oil).

Clinical Assessments: At the initial visit, clinical parameters—including Plaque Index (PI), Gingival Index (GI), Pocket Depth (PD), and Clinical Attachment Level (CAL) were recorded. Additionally, unstimulated saliva samples were collected from patients prior to the procedure for the estimation of MMP-8 levels.

PI:¹⁶ Measured by examining soft debris and mineralized deposits on the teeth with the help of the explorer. Four surfaces (buccal, lingual, mesial and distal) of each tooth will be given a score from 0-3. PI score was obtained by dividing total score obtained by the number of surfaces examined. **GI:**¹⁶ Each of the four gingival areas of the tooth (buccal, lingual, mesial and distal) was given a score from 0-3. GI score was obtained by dividing total score obtained by the number of surfaces examined.

PD and CAL:¹⁷ PD is the distance between the gingival margin to the base of the pocket and CAL was measured from cemento-enamel junction (CEJ) to the base of the pocket. Each tooth was scored in six areas; distofacial, midfacial, mesiofacial, distolingual, midlingual and mesiolingual surfaces. The PD and CAL score was obtained separately by adding all the values and dividing by number of teeth examined. Both the measurements were recorded by using University of North Carolina-15 periodontal probe (Hufriedy Mfg. Co, LLC, Chicago, IL, USA).

Saliva sample collection: Unstimulated saliva collection was performed by having patients sit upright with their heads slightly tilted forward, allowing saliva to naturally pool in the floor of the mouth and then passively drool into a sterile disposable Eppendorf tube over a period of up to 15 minutes until at least 3 ml of saliva was obtained. This method ensures a sufficient volume for accurate MMP-8 analysis using the ELISA method. Patients were advised to abstain from food for at least 2 hours prior to sample collection.

Study procedure: Initially, patients underwent supragingival scaling using a piezoelectric ultrasonic scaler (Woodpecker® UDS-P, Guilin, PRC) to remove plaque and calculus, followed by a two-week

recall for subgingival instrumentation. Full mouth subgingival SRP was performed on the same day under local anesthesia (2% Lidocaine with 1:100,000 epinephrine) using area-specific Gracey curettes (Hufriedy Mfg. Co, LLC, Chicago, IL, USA).

Randomization was performed using a computer-generated random number sequence. Patients were allocated to Group I treated with SRP + Ozonated Olive Oil (Ozonoid ADC, Inc, Mumbai, India) or Group II treated with SRP+ Placebo Oil (B Loyal, Vilaksi enterprises, Kanpur, India) via sealed, opaque envelopes to maintain allocation concealment.

After debridement, each quadrant was isolated and dried using cotton rolls. Depending on the assigned group, patients received subgingival oil applications using a disposable 5-mL plastic syringe equipped with a 24-gauge needle, featuring a 0.55-mm diameter and a bent tip. Oil was then applied to all six sites of each tooth until overflow is seen at gingival margin, ensuring complete subgingival coverage. (Figure-2). Blinding of both patient and operator was ensured using identical opaque syringes for both treatments.

Fig.2: (A)- Ozonated Olive Oil (Ozonoid ADC) (B) Placebo Oil (B Loyal Mineral Oil)

(C) Masked syringes of Ozonated Olive Oil and Placebo Oils (D) Application

Patients were instructed to avoid eating, drinking, or rinsing for at least 30 minutes post-application. Post-operative oral hygiene instructions were given and patients were recalled after 3 months. All the clinical parameters were recorded and saliva sample

collection was done at baseline and 3 months postoperatively.

Salivary MMP-8 (sMMP-8) estimation: The collected saliva samples were centrifuged in disposable tubes for 20 minutes at 1000 g at 2-8°C, and the supernatant was collected for analysis.¹⁸ (Figur-3)

Fig-3: (A) ELISA kit reagents (B) Color change to blue after addition of substrate reagent (C) Color change from blue to yellow after addition of stop solution (D) Final preparation for optical density reading (E) ELISA analyser.

Statistical Analysis: -

Statistical Package for Social Sciences [SPSS] for Windows Version 22.0. (IBM Corp, Armonk, NY, USA) was used to perform statistical analyses. Independent Student t Test was used to compare the mean values of different clinical parameters & salivary MMP-8 levels between 2 groups at Baseline & 3 Months period.

Pearson's correlation test was used to determine the relationship between clinical parameters & salivary

MMP-8 levels between 2 groups at Baseline & 3 Months period. Stepwise multiple linear regression analysis was performed to predict the salivary MMP-8 levels using the clinical parameters in each group. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The age of the recruited patients ranged from 25 to 55 years, with a mean age of 41.20 ± 7.32 years in Group I and 40.45 ± 8.79 years in Group II. There was no statistically significant difference between the mean ages of both groups ($p=0.84$). Group I comprised 9 males (45%) and 11 females (55%),

while Group II included 10 males (50%) and 10 females (50%).

At baseline, Group I had a mean PI score of 1.75 ± 0.28 , while Group II had a mean score of 1.62 ± 0.30 , resulting in a mean difference of 0.13 between the groups (Table-1). After 3 months, the

mean PI scores decreased to 0.80 ± 0.23 for Group I and 0.77 ± 0.24 for Group II, with a reduced mean difference of 0.04. The differences in PI scores between the groups were not statistically significant at both baseline ($p = 0.17$) and 3 months ($p = 0.64$) (Table-2).

Table - 1: Comparison of mean values of different clinical parameters between 2 groups at baseline period using Independent Student t Test

Parameters	Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean Diff	p-value
PI	Group I	20	1.75	0.28	0.13	0.17
	Group II	20	1.62	0.30		
GI	Group I	20	1.81	0.45	-0.08	0.49
	Group II	20	1.89	0.26		
PD	Group I	20	5.41	0.38	0.08	0.59
	Group II	20	5.33	0.54		
CAL	Group I	20	5.68	0.49	-0.11	0.51
	Group II	20	5.79	0.56		

* $P < 0.05$ is considered as Statistically Significant

Regarding GI, Group I had a baseline mean score of 1.81 ± 0.45 , and Group II had a mean score of 1.89 ± 0.26 , with a mean difference of -0.08 ($p = 0.49$), indicating no statistical significance

(Table-1). At 3-months post-operative, the mean GI scores were 0.69 ± 0.19 for Group I and 0.75 ± 0.22 for Group II, with a mean difference of -0.06 ($p = 0.36$), which was also not statistically significant (Table-2).

Table - 2: Comparison of mean values of different clinical parameters between 2 groups at 3 months using Independent Student t Test

Parameters	Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean Diff	p-value
PI	Group I	20	0.80	0.23	0.04	0.64
	Group II	20	0.77	0.24		
GI	Group I	20	0.69	0.19	-0.06	0.36
	Group II	20	0.75	0.22		
PD	Group I	20	3.25	0.44	-0.54	0.001*
	Group II	20	3.79	0.45		
CAL	Group I	20	3.71	0.49	-0.58	<0.001*
	Group II	20	4.28	0.46		

* $P < 0.05$ is considered as Statistically Significant

The mean PD at baseline was 5.41 ± 0.38 mm for Group I and 5.33 ± 0.54 mm for Group II, with a mean difference of 0.08 mm (Table-1). After 3 months, both groups experienced significant reductions in PD, with mean values of 3.25 ± 0.44 mm for Group I and 3.79 ± 0.45 mm for Group II, resulting in a mean difference of -0.54 mm ($p = 0.001$) (Table-2).

Baseline CAL was 5.68 ± 0.49 mm for Group I and 5.79 ± 0.56 mm for Group II (Table-1). At 3 months,

there were significant reductions in CAL, with mean values of 3.71 ± 0.49 mm for Group I and 4.28 ± 0.46 mm for Group II ($p < 0.001$). (Table-2)

sMMP-8 levels at baseline were 6.34 ± 1.11 ng/ml for Group I and 6.41 ± 1.01 ng/ml for Group II. After 3 months, significant decreases in sMMP-8 levels were observed, with Group I showing a mean of 1.30 ± 0.62 ng/ml and Group II a mean of 2.61 ± 0.91 ng/ml ($p < 0.001$) (Table-3).

Table - 3: Comparison of mean sMMP-8 levels (in ng/ml) between 2 groups at baseline and 3 months using Independent Student t Test

Parameters	Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean Diff	p-value
sMMP8 (Baseline)	Group I	20	6.34	1.11	-0.07	0.85
	Group II	20	6.41	1.01		
sMMP8 (3 months)	Group I	20	1.30	0.62	-1.31	<0.001*
	Group II	20	2.61	0.91		

* P < 0.05 is considered as Statistically Significant

Discussion: Scaling and root planing is a fundamental non-surgical treatment for periodontal disease, aiming to restore gingival health by eliminating sources of inflammation such as plaque, calculus, and endotoxins. While SRP is effective, it may not completely eradicate all periodontopathic bacteria, particularly in challenging areas like furcations, grooves, concavities, and deep pockets. Studies have shown that non-surgical periodontal therapy significantly improves clinical parameters and patient-reported outcomes, reinforcing its status as the gold standard in periodontal treatment. However, the success of such treatments can be influenced by factors including the complexity of tooth anatomy and the presence of deep periodontal pockets.^{19,20}

In the present study, individuals aged between 25 and 55 years with periodontitis were divided into two groups. Clinical parameters were documented, and saliva specimens were collected preoperatively. Both groups underwent SRP with Group I received ozonated olive oil, while Group II received a placebo oil. At the 3-month postoperative follow-up, clinical parameters were reassessed, and saliva samples were recollected. Salivary MMP-8 levels were analysed using ELISA methodology. The results indicated that both groups experienced significant improvements in clinical parameters and reductions in salivary MMP-8 levels. However, Group I, which received ozonated olive oil, demonstrated a more pronounced decrease in MMP-8 levels compared to Group II.

In our study, no additional oral hygiene aids or modifications to brushing techniques were recommended, whereas prior research advised patients to use supplementary oral hygiene methods to enhance plaque control and promote gingival healing. In the present study, both groups exhibited similar mean PI and GI scores at baseline and after 3 months. Group II demonstrated slightly higher mean PI and GI

scores compared to Group I; however, this difference was not statistically significant. The greater reduction in PI and GI scores observed in Group I is likely attributable to the combined effect of mechanical plaque control and the adjunctive use of ozonated olive oil. These findings align with previous studies indicating that the adjunctive use of ozonated olive oil with SRP over a three-month period enhances periodontal health outcomes.^{21,22}

In the present study, Group I exhibited significantly higher PPD and CAL values compared to Group II. This finding is in accordance with previous study by Katti et al. where they demonstrated that the adjunctive use of ozonated olive oil with SRP resulted in significant improvements in clinical parameters over time.²³ Similarly, Patel PV et al. reported reductions in PPD and CAL at 8 weeks post-operatively with the use of ozonated olive oil application.²⁴ These findings suggest that ozonated olive oil, when used alongside mechanical plaque control methods, can effectively enhance periodontal health outcomes. However, a systematic review by Colombo et al. did not find a significant reduction in clinical parameters such as PPD) and CAL when comparing the adjunctive use of ozonated olive oil to standard treatments.²⁵ In the present study, salivary MMP-8 levels were assessed using the ELISA method at baseline and after a 3-month follow-up. The results demonstrated a statistically significant greater reduction in mean MMP-8 levels in the ozone-treated group compared to the control group at the 3-month follow-up. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that adjunctive use of ozonated olive oil with scaling and root planing (SRP) enhances the reduction of MMP-8 levels in patients with periodontitis. A study by Nardi et al. demonstrated that non-surgical periodontal therapy supplemented with an ozonated olive oil-based mouthwash led to a significant reduction in salivary MMP-8 levels over a

3-month period. This suggests that ozonated olive oil may enhance the effectiveness of standard periodontal treatments.²⁶ In a microbiological study, Lendhey et al. observed a significant reduction in anaerobic bacterial colony-forming units (CFUs) one month after the subgingival application of ozonated oil.²⁷ In an in vivo study conducted by Herawati et al., evaluated the impact of ozonated olive oil on the healing process in periodontitis induces Sprague Dawley rats and concluded that topical application of ozonated olive oil significantly increased the number of osteoblasts and blood vessels, indicating enhanced bone regeneration and wound healing.²⁸

Tualzik T et al evaluated efficacy of ozonated olive oil and Photo-biomodulation in gingival depigmented wounds and found that application of ozonated olive oil enhanced initial healing when compared to photo-biomodulation alone.²⁹ In a study by Kumar T et al., the twice-daily application of ozonized olive oil resulted in the regression of aphthous ulcerations, herpes labialis, oral candidiasis, and angular cheilitis, while patients with oral lichen planus experienced improvements in signs and symptoms.³⁰ Ozone therapy has been recognized for its antimicrobial properties, particularly in acidic environments where its efficacy is enhanced. While pH levels can influence MMP activity, with certain pH conditions potentially enhancing or inhibiting their function.²² Bocci et al. have suggested that ozone therapy may progressively inhibit MMP secretion and emphasized that a prolonged application of ozone therapy, lasting at least six months, is necessary for effectively managing periodontitis.³¹

However, there are some limitations in the present study. The ozonated olive oil was applied only once on the day of SRP. Unlike other studies where ozonated olive oil was applied periodically during the follow-up period, our study did not include subsequent applications. Participants were not provided with supplementary oral hygiene aids or modifications to their brushing techniques. The follow-up period was limited to 3 months. Another limitation of the present study is that the antimicrobial effect of ozonated olive oil on subgingival bacterial counts was not analyzed. A longer follow-up might be necessary to fully assess the long-term effects and sustainability of the treatment outcomes. The study's

sample size was relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Larger studies are needed to confirm these results.

CONCLUSION

the adjunctive use of ozonated olive oil with SRP demonstrated a significant reduction in salivary MMP-8 levels with concomitant improvement in PD and CAL values over a 3-month period, indicating enhanced periodontal health compared to SRP alone. However, further long-term studies are warranted to substantiate these results and explore the potential of ozonated olive oil as a standard adjunct in periodontal treatment.

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